

Prediction of Academic Performance by Measuring Autonomy for Learning in an Engineering Program

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Abstract

We applied a test that maps 10 distinct aspects of Autonomy for Learning to 69 students entering Engineering programs in a school of Engineering and then followed that group into their first two semesters. The test was LASSI, Learning Strategies Inventory, used by hundreds of institutions around the world in order to detect and provide advice to students that might show deficiencies in their learning strategies. The aspects are Anxiety, Attitude, Concentration, Information Processing, Motivation, Selecting Main Ideas, Self-testing, Assessment Strategy, Time Management and Use of Academic Resources. We analyzed how each of the 10 aspects, all considered important to the development of students in higher education, impacted on their academic performance as measured by their final grades in 10 courses of their first two semesters in Engineering. Those final grades are the results of a series of assessments, ranging from written exams to activities in class and to projects, varying from course to course. Pearson correlation was used as the main tool in studying how the aspects measured by LASSI are related with those final grades. Results revealed correlations above the noise level for the aspects Concentration and Motivation and the grades obtained, mainly in STEM (quantitative) courses. These findings provide insights into identifying the key aspects of learning strategies that should be fostered among students in Engineering programs to enhance academic performance.

Keywords: Autonomy for Learning; Engineering Education; Learning Strategies; Correlation.

1 Introduction

Academic success of students stands as a pivotal variable for any higher education institution, often serving as a metric for institutional performance (Alyahyan & Düstegör, 2020) and directly linked to dropout rates, a phenomenon imposing significant financial losses on universities (Gallego, Cobos & Gallego, 2021). Thus, the investigation of factors predicting or influencing academic performance of higher education students has emerged as an important research agenda at the intersection of psychological sciences and education (Costa & Fleith, 2019).

Before presenting the factors that have been considered relevant to the academic success of higher education students, it is important to make a remark. According to York, Gibson & Rankin (2015), the term academic success has appeared in various research studies as an amorphous construct, encompassing educational outcomes ranging from degree attainment to students' moral development. Thus, it is crucial to clarify what is considered academic success in this study, which will be addressed in the following sections.

O'Connor & Paunonen (2007) suggest that intelligence is not the best predictor for the performance of higher education students. This finding, corroborated by two other studies (Busato et al., 2000, and Resing & Drenth, 2007), may be explained by the fact that university entrants are predominantly selected based on intelligence. Thus, other aspects become necessary to predict academic performance.

Besides intelligence, other factors have proven relevant to academic performance in higher education courses: students' personality (Kappe & Van der Flier, 2012), their motivation and study habits (O'Connor & Paunonen, 2007), sociodemographic characteristics (Helal et al., 2018), and the students' environment, described as class type, semester duration and type of program (Hamoud, Hashim & Awadh, 2018). Among these factors, we will

describe some results obtained in studies on the different personality traits of students, as they may be related to the aspects of autonomy for learning investigated in this research.

The primary theoretical model used to analyse the influence of personality traits on academic success is the Five-Factor Model of personality (O'Connor & Paunonen, 2007; Mammadov, 2021). According to the model, the five major personality factors - Neuroticism, Extraversion, Openness to Experience, Agreeableness, and Conscientiousness - constitute the highest level of the personality hierarchy. Thus, they encompass all other possible personality traits, which are found at a lower level of hierarchy.

Among the Big Five factors, Conscientiousness has been consistently associated with post-secondary academic success. Several studies have identified positive correlations between this factor and various indicators of academic performance such as GPA (Grade Point Average – the weighted average of the grades for each course in the program). According to O'Connor & Paunonen (2007), "the relation between Conscientiousness and academic performance has often been interpreted in terms of motivation; conscientious students are thought to be more motivated to perform well academically than are less conscientious students". Apparently, the ability to focus on a task in an organized and results-oriented manner, which characterizes Conscientiousness, tends to lead to better academic performance.

Considering this scenario, this study investigated possible correlations between 10 different aspects related to students' autonomy for learning and their academic performance in the first year of an Engineering program.

2 Data

We use three sets of data, collected from LASSI (Weinstein, Palmer, Acee, 2016) and from the final grades of 69 students of the Engineering courses at Insper, an institution for higher learning located in São Paulo, Brazil. Those students were the ones that took the LASSI at entrance in college in February 2023, concluded the first semester in June 2023 and the second semester in November 2023. All students entering Insper in that semester took the test, via an online set of questions. About 300 students took the test, including Business and Administration, Economics, Engineering, Law, and Computer Science, but we included in our research only those students that finished the first and second semesters in Engineering (Mechanics, Mechatronics and Computer Engineering).

LASSI measures 10 aspects that are deemed important for the Autonomy of Learning (Weinstein, Palmer, Acee, 2016). We briefly describe these aspects in what follows.

- **Anxiety.** The tension or worriedness of a student when approaching academic tasks.
- **Attitude.** Ability to act based on interests and reasons for succeeding in academic life.
- **Concentration.** Ability to direct and maintain attention to academic activities.
- **Information Processing.** Student can create means to promote understanding and recall.
- **Motivation.** Student accepts responsibility for conducting tasks related to academic success.
- **Selecting Main Ideas.** Ability to extract meaningful information from text or data.
- **Self-testing.** Ability to ask questions that help revise and review topics for activities or exams.
- **Test Strategies.** Ability to use strategies and of taking and preparing for exams or assignments.
- **Time Management.** Student develops methods for the organization of study.
- **Using Academic Resources.** Knowledge or willingness to look for and use academic resources provided by the institution.

The grades obtained in the ten aspects measured by LASSI were compared to the final grades of ten course units, taken in the first and second semesters of Engineering at Insper. Those course units are described briefly now.

First Semester

- **Software Design.** Fundamentals of programming and algorithms.
- **Grand Challenges of Engineering.** Relationships between science, society, and ethics.
- **Instrumentation and Measurement.** Use of tools for measuring and of measuring techniques.
- **Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World.** Mathematical and numerical modelling and simulation of dynamic systems.
- **Design Nature.** Design, prototyping, and fabrication of a product.

Second Semester

- **Activation of Electric Systems.** Concepts, components, and workings of an electric circuit.
- **Data Science.** Statistics and probability.
- **Co-Design of Apps.** User-oriented design and production of software.
- **Physics of Movement.** Cinematics and dynamics of moving bodies.
- **Mathematics of Variation.** Limits, derivative, and integrals of functions of one variable. Differential equations and Linear Algebra.

3 Methodology

To assess the relation between Autonomy for Learning and academic performance for the two first semesters of the Engineering course, we use the Pearson correlation coefficient, defined in the following way for two variables x and y , with n measures x_i and y_i , $i = 1, \dots, n$:

$$\rho = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})(y_i - \bar{y})}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (x_i - \bar{x})^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}} \quad (1)$$

where \bar{x} is the average of x and \bar{y} is the average of y . The Pearson correlation is used to measure the linear correlation between two variables. In our set of data, when calculating the Pearson coefficient between LASSI and grades, x_i are the LASSI score for each student in the sample for a particular aspect of autonomy for learning, and y_i is the final grade obtained by the same student in a certain course unit. In order to visualize the results, we also use a network representation based on asset trees, by selecting only connections that are above a certain threshold. We also use a centrality measure to classify results by this criterium.

4 Results

In what follows, we shall adopt the following indices for the variables being measured, as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Variables and indices.

Aspects of the LASSI		Course Units	
Anxiety	1	Software Design	A
Attitude	2	Grand Challenges of Engineering	B
Concentration	3	Measuring and Instrumentation	C
Information Processing	4	Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World	D
Motivation	5	Design Nature	E
Selecting Main Ideas	6	Activation of Electric Systems	F
Self-testing	7	Data Science	G
Test Strategies	8	Co-Design of Apps	H
Time Management	9	Physics of Movement	I
Using Academic Resources	10	Mathematics of Variation	J

We first discuss the correlation between the ten aspects of Autonomy for Learning measured by LASSI. Below, we show the correlation matrix between these variables (Table 2), highlighting the ones above correlation 0.4 and those above correlation 0.3. Reminding ourselves that this is a symmetric matrix, and thus one that shows the same information twice, we only highlight the values below the main diagonal.

Most correlations above 0.2 are considered to convey meaningful information about how correlated two aspects are to one another. Results seem to show stronger correlations between Attitude and Concentration to many of the other aspects. Selecting Main Ideas and Time management also appear as having stronger correlations with some of the other aspects measured by LASSI.

Table 2. Correlation between aspects of the LASSI.

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10
1	1,00	0,16	0,31	0,02	-0,10	0,45	-0,21	0,25	0,02	0,05
2	0,16	1,00	0,43	0,26	0,49	0,39	0,21	0,22	0,46	0,29
3	0,31	0,43	1,00	0,10	0,43	0,43	0,11	0,41	0,56	0,01
4	0,02	0,26	0,10	1,00	0,24	0,21	0,40	0,03	0,19	0,46
5	-0,10	0,49	0,43	0,24	1,00	0,30	0,35	0,27	0,44	0,27
6	0,45	0,39	0,43	0,21	0,30	1,00	0,11	0,47	0,34	0,23
7	-0,21	0,21	0,11	0,40	0,35	0,11	1,00	0,11	0,22	0,25
8	0,25	0,22	0,41	0,03	0,27	0,47	0,11	1,00	0,32	0,05
9	0,02	0,46	0,56	0,19	0,44	0,34	0,22	0,32	1,00	0,18
10	0,05	0,29	0,01	0,46	0,27	0,23	0,25	0,05	0,18	1,00

We now look at the correlations of the 10 course units of the first and second semester (Table 3). Again, we highlighted higher correlations only for the data below the main diagonal of the matrix.

Table 3. Correlation between course units.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
A	1,00	0,34	0,63	0,52	0,05	0,43	0,49	0,31	0,60	0,61
B	0,34	1,00	0,38	0,46	0,10	0,18	0,45	0,30	0,28	0,33
C	0,63	0,38	1,00	0,42	0,25	0,54	0,65	0,38	0,73	0,67
D	0,52	0,46	0,42	1,00	0,15	0,30	0,51	0,29	0,49	0,55
E	0,05	0,10	0,25	0,15	1,00	0,22	0,22	0,36	0,14	0,19
F	0,43	0,18	0,54	0,30	0,22	1,00	0,60	0,29	0,65	0,60
G	0,49	0,45	0,65	0,51	0,22	0,60	1,00	0,40	0,69	0,67
H	0,31	0,30	0,38	0,29	0,36	0,29	0,40	1,00	0,27	0,41
I	0,60	0,28	0,73	0,49	0,14	0,65	0,69	0,27	1,00	0,84
J	0,61	0,33	0,67	0,55	0,19	0,60	0,67	0,41	0,84	1,00

The first five course units are of the first semester of the Engineering program and the last five are of the second semester. Results show the average of the correlations of the final grades of students in a course unit compared with the final grades of the same students in another course unit. Correlations are now, in average, higher than the ones between aspects of the LASSI.

Looking at correlations within the first semester (top left sector of the matrix), one finds strong correlations between final grades of Software Design and Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World and other course

units where Mathematics is important. There is less correlation of course units where Mathematics is not necessarily present.

Correlations between course units of the second semester (bottom right sector of the matrix) are generally stronger, except for Co-Design of Apps, where Mathematics is not central. Note the very strong correlation of grades obtained in Physics of Movement and Mathematics of Variation.

Looking at the correlations between course units of different semesters, bottom left sector of the matrix, one can see strong correlations between Physics of Movement with Software Design and with Measuring and Instrumentation, and between Mathematics of Variation and those same course units. There are strong correlations between other inter-semester course units, except with Design Nature.

We now turn to the main concern of this article, which is to study the correlations between aspects of the LASSI and course units (Table 4). Now the correlation matrix is asymmetric and so we highlight higher values in the whole matrix. We also highlight meaningful negative correlations, those that are below what is expected for random data. Sectors divide course units of the first and second semesters.

Table 4. Correlation between aspects of the LASSI and course units.

	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	J
1	0,14	0,14	-0,03	0,13	-0,15	-0,06	-0,02	-0,01	0,01	-0,08
2	0,18	0,20	0,21	0,13	0,18	-0,02	0,15	-0,09	0,14	0,14
3	0,33	0,27	0,37	0,41	0,21	0,06	0,19	-0,11	0,37	0,22
4	-0,01	0,02	-0,04	-0,10	-0,01	-0,18	0,03	-0,01	-0,11	-0,03
5	0,22	0,25	0,22	0,22	0,12	0,12	0,17	-0,24	0,21	0,20
6	0,14	0,24	0,03	0,06	-0,06	0,11	0,06	-0,13	0,10	-0,03
7	-0,17	0,05	-0,09	-0,04	0,07	-0,20	-0,29	-0,18	-0,29	-0,16
8	0,09	0,33	0,15	0,31	0,09	0,13	0,16	0,00	0,08	0,11
9	0,18	0,20	0,23	0,24	0,24	0,05	0,02	-0,14	0,13	0,13
10	-0,07	0,03	-0,17	-0,22	-0,13	-0,01	-0,04	-0,08	-0,02	0,03

Correlations now have smaller values, even meaningful negative ones. Correlations above 0.3 can be found between Concentration and Software Design, Measuring and Instrumentation, Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World, and Physics of Movement. Other correlations above 0.3 appear between Test Strategies and Grand Challenges of Engineering and Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World. There are also some meaningful anticorrelations between Self-testing and some course units of the second semester. Course units that are most correlated with the aspects measured by LASSI are Grand Challenges of Engineering and Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World. Co-Design of Apps is weakly negatively correlated with most aspects of the LASSI.

What we may conclude from the data collected and analysed is that Concentration seems to be correlated with grades obtained in some course units of the first semester, and that this correlation weakens for course units of the second semester, except for Physics of Movement and, to a lesser extent, to Mathematics of Variation.

5 Network Structure

Another way to visualize this data is to use networks, which are basically a number of nodes (usually represented by dots) connected by edges (Newman, 2010). In the case of the present work, each dot is an aspect of Autonomy for Learning measured by LASSI (red dots) or a course unit (blue dots for first semester and purple dots for second semester). Edges are given by the correlation between nodes. Since correlation is

symmetric, edges are undirected. A network can be built by using thresholds, which are values of correlation above which edges are represented, with the omission of edges below the threshold value and of those nodes without any edges. This is usually called an asset graph (Onnela et al, 2003).

Figure 1 shows the asset trees resulting from choosing thresholds of correlation above 0.8, above 0.7 and above 0.6. Note that the only correlations above those threshold values are ones between course units.

Figure 2 shows the asset trees resulting from choosing threshold 0.5. One may see now the first connection between aspects of the LASSI, between Concentration and Time Management, and an intensification of connections between many of the course units.

At the edge of noise level, which is about correlations below 0.3, we have the asset graph for threshold 0.4 (figure 3), where there are clearly two clusters, one of aspects of the LASSI, and another of course units. One may also see the first connection between both clusters, between Concentration and Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World. Other asset trees, below threshold 0.3, not shown here, also describe two clusters, with increasing connections among their members, and also an increase in connections between clusters.

Figure 1. Asset graphs of course units with correlation thresholds above 0.8, above 0.7 and above 0.6

Figure 2. Asset graph for threshold 0.5

Threshold 0.4

Figure 3. Asset graph for threshold 0.4

At the cluster of aspects of the LASSI, we may identify a tighter clustering between what are aspects related with Resilience or Conscientiousness, namely Concentration, Attitude, Time Management, and Motivation. At lower values of the threshold, this subcluster connects with performance in course units. One measure of how central a node is in a network is Node Degree (Newman, 2010), which is the number of edges of a certain node, but this depends on the choice of threshold. Another measure is Node Strength, which is the sum of the weights of edges connected to a node. In the case of correlation matrices, it is the sum of the line of a matrix, or of the column, related with a node. Table 5 shows the Node Strengths of each of the nodes in our network, subdivided by correlation matrix. The first subdivision is between aspects of the LASSI with themselves. Selecting Main Ideas, Attitude, Concentration, Time Management, and Motivation appear as strongly connected in that cluster.

Table 5. Node strengths ordered.

LASSI - LASSI	
Aspects of the LASSI	NS
Selecting Main Ideas	2,93
Attitude	2,91
Concentration	2,79
Time Management	2,73
Motivation	2,69
Test Strategies	2,13
Information Processing	1,91
Using Academic Resources	1,79
Self-testing	1,55
Anxiety	0,95
LASSI - Course Units	
Aspects of the LASSI	NS
Concentration	2,32
Motivation	1,49
Test Strategies	1,45
Time Management	1,28
Attitude	1,22
Selecting Main Ideas	0,52
Anxiety	0,07
Information Processing	-0,44
Using Academic Resources	-0,68
Self-testing	-1,3

Course Units - Course Units	
Course Units	NS
Mathematics of Variation	4,87
Physics of Movement	4,69
Data Science	4,68
Measuring and Instrumentation	4,65
Software Design	3,98
Activation of Electric Systems	3,81
Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World	3,69
Co-Design of Apps	3,01
Grand Challenges of Engineering	2,82
Design Nature	1,68
Course Units - LASSI	
Course Units	NS
Grand Challenges of Engineering	1,73
Modelling and Simulation of the Physical World	1,14
Software Design	1,03
Measuring and Instrumentation	0,88
Physics of Movement	0,62
Design Nature	0,56
Mathematics of Variation	0,53
Data Science	0,43
Activation of Electric Systems	0,00
Co-Design of Apps	-0,99

The second subdivision shows Node Strengths between course units, with the prevalence of STEM related ones. The third subdivision shows aspects of the LASSI that have the strongest connections with course units, which

highlights Concentration as the most central node. The fourth subdivision shows node strengths of course units with LASSI aspects, with low values of centrality.

6 Conclusion

Our results show that there is a measurable correlation of Concentration with most course units related with STEM, or quantitative aspects. Also, Concentration relates to a small subcluster of aspects of Autonomy for Learning which can be compared with Resilience and to Conscientiousness, previously identified with academic performance in the works of O'Connor & Paunonen (2007).

As side results, we discovered that the correlations between aspects of the LASSI are not strong, what substantiate that those ten aspects are independent components of the Autonomy for Learning (Weinstein, Palmer, Acee, 2016), and strong correlations of course units that are quantitative driven.

Results suggest that researchers on Engineering Education should concentrate on developing Concentration of students as an important predictor of academic success, as measured by final grades in course units. We quote from the LASSI Manual (Weinstein, Palmer, Acee, 2016): "Concentration helps students to focus their attention on school-related activities, such as studying and listening in class, rather than on distracting thoughts, emotions, feelings, or situations. ... Learning techniques for focusing attention and maintaining concentration help students implement effective learning strategies and can make learning and studying both more effective and more efficient."

Further work may include following the same students on their third semester of academic progress, studying students for other courses, such as Business and Administration, Economics, Law, and Computer Science and comparing with the results of Engineering Students. Another line of work is investigating how aspects of the Autonomy for Learning, such as Concentration, may be developed in college students, and test if an increase in this aspect leads to better academic results.

Since correlation does not imply causation, we also plan to address the issue of causality, an aspect that cannot be measured by correlation alone, to check if there could be other factors not considered that help explain our findings. Transfer Entropy, that is derived from Shannon Entropy from Information Theory, will be used as a tool.

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